

Biomimetic Nano-Composite Actuator Based on Fullerene-Reinforced Nafion Ionic Polymer

J H Jung, V Sridhar, I K Oh

School of Mechanical Systems Engineering, Chonnam National University
500-757, 300 Yongbong-dong Buk-gu Gwangju, Republic of Korea
ikoh@chonnam.ac.kr

SUMMARY

The nano-composite actuator based on Fullerene and Nafion has been newly developed. The tensile test, IEC, water uptake, and actuation performances at various conditions are tested to define the characteristics of the nano-composite actuator. The novel actuator shows much larger deformation and better performance than pure Nafion based actuator.

Keywords: Fullerene, Nafion, Nano-composite, Actuator, Ionic polymer

Introduction

Natural muscles are one of the most spectacular actuators for walking, flying, and crawling motions in the human body and in animals. Of late, artificial muscles that mimic the actuation mechanism of natural muscles have become a hot issue in biomimetic engineering[1]. Electro-active artificial muscles[2], including conducting polymers[3], carbon nanotubes[4], dielectric elastomers[5], ionic polymer-metal composites[6], electro-strictive paper[7], and ionic liquid bucky gel[8] usually have a large strain, flexibility, and restoration, like natural muscles. The electro-active polymer transducers can be used for artificial organs, bio-medical devices, biomimetic robots, micro-grippers, ambient energy harvesters, and drug delivery systems.

Among the electro-active polymers, the ionic polymer metal-composite (IPMC) actuators have many attractive advantages[9] such as a large stroke with a low voltage, bio-compatibility, bio-mimetic activation, and low power consumption. However, IPMC actuators exhibit the straightening-back phenomenon[10] under step inputs due to the diffusion of water molecules and the severe distortion of harmonic responses at low-frequency excitation. Also, the low blocking force and bandwidth frequency become major barriers for practical application of IPMC actuators.

A new class of nano-composite actuators with controllable properties such as mechanical stiffness, conductivity, and dielectric constant can be achieved by combining electro-active polymers with nano-sized fillers including carbon nanotubes[11, 12], carbon nanofibers[13], montmorillonite nanoclays, and nanosilica. Buckminsterfullerene, C-60, is the smallest nano-particle of fullerene molecules in which no two pentagons share an edge. It is also the most common in terms of natural occurrence, as it often can be found in soot. The fullerene[14] was discovered in 1985 by Robert Curl, Harold Kroto, and Richard Smalley who named it after Richard Buckminster Fuller, whose geodesic domes resemble the fullerene. Tasaki et al.[15] fabricated fullerene-Nafion composites for high-performance fuel cell membranes.

Wang et al.[16] synthesized new nano-particles of the functionalized fullerenes as additives for proton conducting membranes. Until now, fullerenes that pertain to the carbon molecules of C₂₈, C₃₂, C₄₄, C₅₀, C₅₈, C₆₀, C₇₀, C₈₀, C₈₂, C₁₈₀ and C₂₄₀ have not been used for electro-active polymers, although they have many interesting properties, such as high surface area, porosity, thermal stability, non-toxicity, biocompatibility, and hydrophilic functionalization, which can be promising in electro-active polymers.

In this study, a biomimetic nano-composite actuator that is based on the fullerene-reinforced ionic polymer membrane is newly developed. To investigate the effects of the fullerene reinforcement, many electro-mechanical tests have been performed including the stress-strain curve, dynamic mechanical analysis, ionic exchangeable capacity, proton conductivity, and water uptake ratio. Also, dramatic improvements of the fullerene-based ionic polymer actuators are described with step responses, harmonic responses, and blocking forces.

Principle and Fabrication of IPMC

Fabrication the membrane

As a base ionic polymer, DuPont™ Nafion PFSA polymer dispersions, which contain perfluorosulfonic acid/PTFE copolymer in the acid (H⁺) form with alcohol and water, are used. Buckminsterfullerene, C-60, with a purity of 99.5% was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Since the simple mixing of fullerene with commercially available Nafion dispersions, which primarily consist of alcohol and water, results in the poor dispersion of fullerenes in the nano-composite membrane, two different solvents of ortho-dichlorobenzene and N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) were used for fullerenes and the Nafion film, respectively. First, the Nafion film was obtained by drying DuPont™ Nafion PFSA polymer dispersions in a vacuum oven under a regulated temperature of 80 °C for 12 hours. Then, the dried Nafion film was inserted into the DMAc solution and the Nafion solution was again obtained by stirring for six hours under a temperature of 80 °C. The ortho-dichlorobenzene was inserted into the Nafion solution, and fullerenes with weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5% were agitated in dichlorobenzene for two hours at room temperature. After the addition of the dispersed fullerenes into the as-prepared Nafion-DMAc solution, the mixed solution was stirred for a day. The well-dispersed fullerene-Nafion solutions were dried in the casting mold under a temperature of 120 °C for 12 hours. To reduce the internal residual stresses, the thermal treatment was done under a temperature of 140 °C for two hours.

Fabrication the IPMC

The nano-composite actuator based on the fullerene-reinforced ionic polymer membrane was fabricated through electroless plating of the platinum electrode layers. By using a sand blasting technique, the surfaces of the prepared fullerene-reinforced ionic polymer membrane were roughened for strong adhesion and conductivity between the polymer membrane and platinum electrode layers. After sonicated in de-ionized water for half an hour, the membranes are boiled in 2N HCl for half an hour to remove impurities of the membranes. The next step is to boil the film in de-ionized water for

half an hour for cleaning the HCl acid. The electrode was made through electroless plating based on the platinum-ammine complex salt with 5-time initial compositing process and surface electrode process[17]. At the end of this process, the polymer-metal composite membrane was put in the 1.5N LiCl liquid for over a day to exchange Li⁺ cation with H⁺. The specimens of the final electro-active nano-composite actuators are prepared with the size of 20mm(L)×5mm(W) as shown in Figure 2.

Test for Define Characteristics of Membrane

Stress-Strain curve

At the outset, to validate some improvements in the polymer level, the mechanical and electrical properties of the fullerene-reinforced Nafion membranes were measured in terms of stress-strain curves, water uptake, proton conductivity, and ionic exchange capacity. Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curves of the pure Nafion membrane and fullerene-Nafion membranes with weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5%. The three membranes were prepared with a size of 30mm(L)×5mm(W) for the tensile test to define the Young's modulus and the strength of the membranes. The pure Nafion membrane failed at the maximum stress of 5.37MPa, and the fullerene-Nafion membranes with weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5% failed at the maximum stresses of 6.76MPa and 10.64MPa, respectively. Also, the Young's moduli are listed in Table 1. The Young's modulus of the fullerene-Nafion membrane with a weight percentage of 0.5% doubled in comparison with the pure Nafion membrane. The mechanical stiffness and strength of the fullerene-reinforced Nafion membranes tremendously improved, although only small quantities of nano-particles, in weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5%, were simply added.

Water uptake

Further, the water uptake ratios, proton conductivities, and ionic exchange capacities of the three membranes are listed in Table 1. The water uptake ratio could be calculated through the following equation.

$$\text{Water uptake} = \frac{W_{wet} - W_{dry}}{W_{dry}} \times 100(\%) \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), W_{wet} and W_{dry} are the weights of wet and dry membranes, respectively. The water-uptake ratios of the pure Nafion membrane and of the fullerene-reinforced membranes with weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5% are 16.7%, 18.2%, and 20.8%, respectively. The water-uptake ratios of the fullerene-reinforced membranes increase and the fullerene-reinforced membranes become more hydrophilic. The hydrophilia will make better conditions for clusters of cations and water molecules and could be a main reason why nano-composite actuators show much larger deformations and greater blocking forces

Proton Conductivity

The proton conductivity of ionic polymers is measured with swollen membranes in de-ionized water at room temperature over two hours. The resistance of each sample is measured by using a Zahner Elektrik IM6e impedance analyzer under a maximum voltage of 10mV and an excitation frequency of 100Hz~1MHz. The proton conductivity can be calculated through the following equation.

$$\text{Proton conductivity} = \frac{1}{R(\Omega)} \times \frac{L(\text{cm})}{S(\text{cm}^2)} (\text{S/cm}) \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), R is the resistance from the impedance analyzer, and L and S are the thickness of membranes and the area of the electrode, respectively. The thickness of a membrane is measured at five locations (center, left, right, upper side, and lower side) and the average value is used. As a result, the proton conductivity of the pure Nafion membrane was 6.40×10^{-2} S/cm, while the 0.1% fullerene-Nafion membrane has a proton conductivity of 8.59×10^{-2} S/cm and the 0.5% fullerene-Nafion membrane has a proton conductivity of 11.9×10^{-2} S/cm. The proton conductivity of the fullerene-Nafion membrane with a weight percentage of 0.5% almost increased two times.

Ionic Exchange Capacity

The ionic exchange capacity (IEC) is calculated through Eq. (3). Each membrane is put in 2M of HCl during a day for the ion exchange of H^+ . Then, the films are put in 2M of NaCl for one day for the ion exchange of H^+ with Na^+ cations. Finally, each membrane is washed with de-ionized water until H^+ is removed. The weights of membranes are measured, and dried in the vacuum oven for four hours. The ionic exchange capacity is calculated through the titration method. A 0.01M NaOH with two or three drops of phenolphthalein is used for titration.

$$\text{IEC} = \frac{x \times N_{\text{NaOH}}}{W_{\text{membrane}}} (\text{meq/g}) \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3), x is the quantity (ml) of NaOH and N_{NaOH} is the normality of NaOH. As shown in Table 1, the ionic exchange capacities of three membranes are determined within the error bound of the experiment. This means that the change in the IEC value is negligible because the chemical structures of the ionic polymer itself are not changed, although nano-particles of fullerenes are added into the ionic polymers.

Thermogravimetric Analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of three membranes is undertaken, but the TGA curves are all the same. The fullerene reinforcement does not strongly affect the chemical structure and the thermal stability, while it dramatically improves the proton conductivity and the water-uptake ratio, which result in improvements of the actuation performance, as described in the following sections.

Test for Define Characteristics of Actuator

Experimental Setup

As an electro-active artificial muscle, the fullerene-reinforced nano-composite actuator has been newly developed. The following sections will deal with several tests of the actuation performance including step responses, harmonic responses, and blocking forces in wet-type conditions. The experimental setup for the measurement of motion and actuation is shown in Figure 4. A CCD camera (XC-HR50) and a laser displacement sensor were used for sensing displacements and motions, and a NI-PXI system and a current amplifier (UPM1504) were used for signal generation and actuation for the electro-active artificial muscle.

Actuation test

For simple harmonic responses, time-histories for the tip displacement of three cantilevered actuators under an electrical sinusoidal input signal of a maximum voltage of 1.0 V and an excitation frequency of 1.0 Hz. As shown in Figure 5(a), the 0.5% fullerene-reinforced actuator shows double the tip displacement of the pure Nafion actuator. Figures 5(b) show the maximum positive values of the harmonic responses for various values of the maximum voltage and the excitation frequency. It is observed that the harmonic responses of the fullerene-reinforced nano-composite actuators remarkably improve, as the input voltage increases. Also, the maximum amplitude of the tip displacements decreases, as the excitation frequency increases. The measured responses show that the reinforcement of fullerenes can improve the large deformation per unit input voltage.

The step responses of three electro-active polymers under the DC inputs of 1.0 V are compared, as shown in Figures 6, respectively. The overshoot of the transient responses of the 0.1% fullerene-Nafion actuator become higher and the straitening-back phenomenon[6] that is the main drawback of IPMC actuators is lessened. The relaxation problem originates from the diffusion of the water molecules under the electrical step input. The pure Nafion-based actuator shows that the tip displacement approaches zero, while the 0.1% fullerene-Nafion actuator maintains the steady-state displacement for long time. It is thought that the hydrophilic fullerene-Nafion membrane strongly affects the mobility of the cations and water molecules under the step inputs. It is also a valuable outcome of the reinforcement of the ionic polymer-metal actuator with fullerene

Blocking force

Another main problem of electro-active polymer actuators is that their blocking forces are too low. For real applications of electro-active polymers, the blocking forces should be increased in the future. The blocking force was measured in the dry condition by using a load-cell, while keeping the tip displacement at zero. As shown in Figure 7, The blocking force of the pure Nafion-based actuator under the step input of 3.0 V is 0.078 g_f , while those of the fullerene-reinforced actuators with weight percentages of 0.1% and 0.5% are 0.184 g_f and 0.236 g_f , respectively. The 0.5% fullerene-Nafion actuator shows triple the blocking force in comparison with the pure Nafion-based actuator.

Conclusion

In this study, a biomimetic nano-composite actuator based on the fullerene-reinforced ionic polymer membrane was newly developed to improve the bending performance of ionic polymer-metal actuators. From the presented results, some conclusions can be drawn as follows. The static tensile test and dynamic mechanical analyses show that the stiffness and strength of the fullerene-reinforced composite membrane increased up to about 100% in comparison with the pure polymer membrane. Also, while the ionic exchangeable capacity of the nano-composite film did not change, the proton conductivity and the water-uptake ratio increased, resulting in a high-performance actuator. The harmonic responses of the fullerene-reinforced actuators doubled and frequency responses greatly improved in the low-frequency region. The blocking force of the IPMC actuator dramatically increased up to three times, and also the straightening-back phenomenon of the IPMC actuators can be lessened by adding the nano-particles of fullerenes.

Table 1. Properties of pure Nafion and two fullerene-reinforced membranes.

Type	Young's modulus (MPa)	Proton conductivity (S/Cm)	Water uptake (%)	IEC (<i>meq/g</i>)
Pure Nafion	9.8775	6.40×10^{-2}	16.7	1.65
0.1% Fullerene-Nafion	11.2885	8.59×10^{-2}	18.2	1.68
0.5% Fullerene-Nafion	20.6573	11.9×10^{-2}	20.8	1.61

Figure 1. Concept of fullerene-reinforced ionic polymer.

Figure 2. Three actuators with size of 20mm(L)X5mm(W).

Figure 3. Stress-strain curves for Young's modulus and strength.

Figure 4. Experimental setup for measurement of tip displacement and motions of actuators

(a) Harmonic responses under voltage amplitude of 1.0V and excitation frequency of 1.0Hz

(b) Peak tip displacement of harmonic responses under voltage amplitudes of 1.0V and 2.0V

Figure 5. Maximum tip displacement of three actuators under harmonic responses.

Figure 6. Straightening-back phenomena in long time step responses under input voltage of 1.0V

Figure 7. Blocking forces according to input voltages

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Korea Science and Engineering Foundation(KOSEF) NRL Program grant funded by the Korea government(MEST) (No. R0A-2008-000-20012-0)

References

1. Bar-Cohen, Y. *Biomimetics Biologically Inspired Technologies* Talyor & Fracis New York **2006**.
2. Baughman, R. H. *Science* **2005**, 308, 63.
3. Smela, E. *Adv. Mater.* **2003**, 15, 481.
4. Baughman, R.H.; Cui, C.; Zakhidov, A. A.; Iqbal, Z.; Barisci, J. N.; Spinks, G. M.; Wallace, G. G.; Mazzoldi, A.; De Rossi, D.; Rinzler, A. G.; Jaschinski, O.; Roth, S.; Kertesz, M. *Science* **1999**, 284, 1340.
5. Perline, P.; Kornbluh, R.; Pei Q.; Joseph J. *Science* **2000**, 287, 836.
6. Shahinpoor, M.; Kim, K. J. *Smart Mater. Struct.* **2001**, 10, 819.
7. Kim, J.; Yun, S.; Ounaies, Z. *Macromolecules* **2006**, 39, 4202.
8. Mukai, K.; Asaka, K.; Kiyohara, K.; Sugino, T. Takeuchi, I.; Fukushima T.; Aida T.; *Electrochimica Acta* **2008**, 53, 5555.
9. Kim, K. J.; Shahinpoor, M. *Polymer* **2002**, 43, 797-802.
10. Lu, J.; Kim, S.; Lee, S.; Oh, I. K. *Adv. Func. Mater.* **2008**, 18, 1290.
11. Jung, J. Y.; Oh, I. K. *J. Nanosci. Nanotech.* **2007**, 7, 3740.
12. Landi, B. J.; Raffaele, R. P.; Heben, M. P.; Alleman, J. L.; VanDerveer, W.; Gennett, T. *Nano Letters* **2002**, 2, 1329.
13. Wang, X. L.; Oh, I. K.; Kim, J. B. *Comp. Sci. Tech.* **2009** In press, doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.023
14. Kroto, H. W.; Heath, J. R.; O'Brien, S. C.; Curl R. F.; Smalley R. E. *Nature* **1985**, 318, 162.
15. Tasaki, K.; Gasa, J.; Wang, H. *Polymer* **2007**, 48, 4438
16. Wang, H.; DeSousa, R.; Gasa, J. *J. Membr. Sci.* **2007**, 289, 277.
17. Shahinpoor M.; Kim K. J. *Smart Mater. Struct.* **2003**, 12, 65-79